

Supplemental Figure S1. Sashimi plots showing 118 TA-ASEs as in Figure 1B.

chr1:225695653:225695719:-@chr1:225692693:225692755:-@chr1:225688694:225688772:-

chr3:13661230:13661331:+@chr3:13663275:13663415:+@chr3:13667945:13668079:+

chr2:238289558:238290142:-@chr2:238287279:238287878:-@chr2:238285415:238285987:-

chrX:30742218:30742298:+@chrX:30745583:30745669:+@chrX:30746849:30748725:+

chr10:24762157:24762989:+@chr10:24783429:24783533:+@chr10:24784076:24784125:+

chr3:191087708:191087825:+@chr3:191092851:191093378:+@chr3:191097948:191098063:+

chr8:38586105:38586189:+@chr8:38645075:38645261:+@chr8:38646222:38646337:+

chr1:155033239:155033308:+@chr1:155034380:155034451:+@chr1:155034721:155034845:+

chr11:85425456:85425550:-@chr11:85422156:85422275:-@chr11:85420374:85420543:-

chr10:89475489:89475600:+@chr10:89481513:89481527:+@chr10:89487041:89487246:+

chr2:172563797:172563887:+@chr2:172569277:172569336:+@chr2:172571838:172571861:+

chr1:172520652:172520766:+@chr1:172522400:172522510:+@chr1:172525009:172525163:+

chr1:29385101:29385157:+@chr1:29386934:29386996:+@chr1:29391494:29391670:+

chr8:141684397:141684503:-@chr8:141679826:141679834:-@chr8:141678368:141678523:-

chr11:85429833:85429886:-@chr11:85428526:85428573:-@chr11:85425456:85425550:-

chr16:3705374:3705521:+@chr16:3705850:3705938:+@chr16:3706103:3706186:+

chr18:56001050:56001124:+@chr18:56002710:56002769:+@chr18:56008270:56008401:+

chr12:72287002:72287104:+@chr12:72288105:72288155:+@chr12:72288466:72288663:+

chr7:36466525:36466637:+@chr7:36467916:36467969:+@chr7:36478813:36478899:+

chr11:69954459:69954510:+@chr11:69957232:69957297:+@chr11:69957813:69957868:+

chr1:225706900:225707267:-@chr1:225704898:225705692:-@chr1:225702298:225702602:-

225707268 225706275 225705281 225704288 225703294 225702300
Genomic coordinate (chr1, "-" strand)

chr11:57582866:57582972:+@chr11:57583387:57583473:+@chr11:57583769:57586650:+

chr17:76200909:76200981:+@chr17:76201684:76201819:+@chr17:76202027:76202131:+

chr14:51226575:51227077:-@chr14:51223210:51225348:-@chr14:51221460:51221585:-

chr10:24825703:24825822:+@chr10:24831622:24831699:+@chr10:24833910:24834197:+

chr20:34785781:34785963:+@chr20:34797410:34797820:+@chr20:34800194:34800298:+

chr11:57529269:57529518:+@chr11:57556509:57556627:+@chr11:57558964:57559145:+

chr11:70266506:70266616:+@chr11:70267576:70267686:+@chr11:70269046:70269101:+

chr3:193336658:193336725:+@chr3:193343881:193343991:+@chr3:193349401:193349454:+

chr4:159754680:159754780:+@chr4:159754953:159755042:+@chr4:159756557:159756628:+

chr7:134617739:134618141:+@chr7:134620439:134620516:+@chr7:134625843:134625988:+

chr4:41668578:41668683:+@chr4:41672735:41672809:+@chr4:41673571:41673611:+

chr6:44191302:44191378:+@chr6:44193798:44193904:+@chr6:44195000:44195079:+

chr3:100029247:100029386:+@chr3:100030677:100030721:+@chr3:100034943:100035031:+

chr11:124495567:124495799:+@chr11:124496369:124496505:+@chr11:124496800:124496946:+

chr11:57529269:57529591:+@chr11:57558857:57559145:+@chr11:57561482:57561553:+

chr6:125569428:125569529:+@chr6:125574863:125574901:+@chr6:125583980:125584643:+

chr4:76714843:76715054:+@chr4:76716489:76716509:+@chr4:76720775:76720885:+

chr5:50045985:50046022:+@chr5:50052953:50053049:+@chr5:50055477:50055566:+

chr10:129914755:129914800:-@chr10:129913192:129914271:-@chr10:129911691:129911866:-

chr16:686094:686351:-@chr16:685281:685340:-@chr16:684719:684797:-

chr7:74312263:74312349:+@chr7:74312526:74312628:+@chr7:74313768:74313951:+

chr11:69999163:69999234:+@chr11:70002017:70002094:+@chr11:70003053:70003127:+

chr17:4462853:4463230:-@chr17:4462638:4462751:-@chr17:4461115:4462352:-

chr11:35211382:35211612:+@chr11:35232793:35232996:+@chr11:35236399:35236461:+

chr1:211477425:211477482:+@chr1:211486062:211486177:+@chr1:211486766:211487014:+

chr10:105767935:105768114:+@chr10:105770574:105770666:+@chr10:105777918:105778047:+

chr1:16046229:16046415:+@chr1:16047824:16047883:+@chr1:16051812:16052040:+

chr1:161643750:161643863:+@chr1:161645047:161645103:+@chr1:161647118:161647155:+

chr10:114711242:114711366:+@chr10:114724315:114724383:+@chr10:114799784:114799885:+

114711242 114728970 114746698 114764427 114782155 114799884
Genomic coordinate (chr10), "+" strand

chr17:76198784:76198832:+@chr17:76200737:76200822:+@chr17:76200909:76200981:+

chr10:79796952:79797062:+@chr10:79799962:79799983:+@chr10:79800373:79800455:+

chr6:26459709:26460056:+@chr6:26463025:26463125:+@chr6:26463472:26463753:+

chr1:197621365:197621445:-@chr1:197616185:197616244:-@chr1:197614820:197614873:-

chr9:2650370:2650516:+@chr9:2651415:2651498:+@chr9:2651874:2651954:+

chr1:161008670:161008740:-@chr1:161008341:161008484:-@chr1:161007703:161007865:-

chr4:54265897:54266006:+@chr4:54280782:54280889:+@chr4:54292039:54292132:+

chr1:156909340:156909702:-@chr1:156908210:156908305:-@chr1:156907041:156907288:-

62761199 62743182 62725164 62707147 62689129 62671111
Genomic coordinate (chr10), "-" strand

chr19:50529150:50529379:+@chr19:50534149:50534348:+@chr19:50534271:50534348:+

chr12:112371690:112371834:-@chr12:112371690:112374634:-@chr12:112374964:112375047:-

112375048 112374377 112373706 112373035 112372364 112371692
Genomic coordinate (chr12), "-" strand

chr7:134617739:134618141:+@chr7:134617739:134618828:+@chr7:134625843:134625988:+

chr10:24833910:24834032:+@chr10:24833910:24836772:+@chr10:24834756:24836772:+

24833910 24834482 24835054 24835626 24836198 24836771
Genomic coordinate (chr10), "+" strand

chr2:242162601:242162691:+@chr2:242162601:242163196:+@chr2:242163077:242163196:+

242162601 242162719 242162838 242162957 242163076 242163195
Genomic coordinate (chr2), "+" strand

chr11:830250:830337:+@chr11:830250:830713:+@chr11:830621:830713:+

chr5:179048243:179048398:-@chr5:179047893:179048398:-@chr5:179047893:179048036:-

chr11:830866:831032:+@chr11:830866:831295:+@chr11:831224:831295:+

chr11:118514790:118514892:+@chr11:118514790:118515409:+@chr11:118515365:118515409:+

Supplemental Fig S2. Examples of excluded TA ASEs called by rMATS - high intronic noise. Below are 4 examples of ASEs that rMATS reported as significantly differentially spliced between tumor and normal samples, but the exonic read densities are largely clouded by the intronic read densities.

chr7:75039645:75039743:+@chr7:75042067:75042210:+@chr7:75044163:75044301:+

chr2:241500148:241500527:-@chr2:241496607:241496769:-@chr2:241494283:241494472:-

chr7:64275296:64275422:+@chr7:64291318:64291454:+@chr7:64291829:64292181:+

chr5:138614740:138614818:+@chr5:138615624:138615747:+@chr5:138618428:138618678:+

Supplemental Fig S2. Examples of excluded TA ASEs called by rMATS - complex transcript structure. Below are 4 examples where rMATS reported a differentially spliced ASE in a gene that has complex transcript structure, usually involving more than 4 exons in the region.

chr3:160821215:160821305:-@chr3:160820901:160820993:-@chr3:160801685:160804576:-

chr21:42879877:42879909:-@chr21:42870046:42870116:-@chr21:42861434:42861520:-@chr21:42852403:42852529:-

chr7:102727077:102727211:+@chr7:102727316:102727384:+@chr7:102738746:102739310:+

chr19:9785691:9785776:-@chr19:9771396:9771497:-@chr19:9770055:9770143:-@chr19:9759363:9764557:-

Supplemental Fig S2. Examples of excluded TA ASEs called by rMATS - complex transcript structure. Below shows 2 examples of genes with complex transcript structure, where one exon was reported in multiple exons. In the top panel, the second exon was reported both as one of the pair of mutually exclusive exons (left) and as a skipped exon (right). In the bottom panel, the second exon was reported both as a skipped exon (left) and as one of the pair of mutually exclusive exons (right). Only one representative of these redundant ASEs was reported in each case, typically the most prevalent one based on literature review or the one with the simplest structure.

chr1:225695653:225695719:-@chr1:225692693:225692755:-@chr1:225688694:225688772:-@chr1:225686049:225686106:-

chr1:225695653:225695719:-@chr1:225692693:225692755:-@chr1:225688694:225688772:-

chr15:63334957:63335142:+@chr15:63335905:63336030:+@chr15:63336226:63336351:+

chr15:63334957:63335142:+@chr15:63335905:63336030:+@chr15:63336226:63336351:+@chr15:633349184:633349317:+

Supplemental Figure S3. Example in which multiple transcribed isoforms render ASE analysis ambiguous The sashimi plots are aligned at the corresponding exons in the transcript models in the top panel. Longer and shorter forms of the exons E1, E2, E3 and E6 are treated as the same.

Skipped exon: chr19:9771396:9771550:-@chr19:9770055:9770143:-@chr19:9768685:9768811:-

Mutually exclusive exons: chr19:9785691:9785776:-@chr19:9771396:9771497:-@chr19:9770055:9770143:-@chr19:9759363:9764557:-

Skipped exon: chr19:9785691:9785720:-@chr19:9770055:9770143:-@chr19:9768685:9768811:-

Skipped exon: chr19:9785691:9785758:-@chr19:9771396:9771550:-@chr19:9767223:9767329:-

Supplemental Figure S3. (continued)

Skipped exon: chr19:9771396:9771550:-@chr19:9770055:9770143:-@chr19:9767223:9767329:-

Mutually exclusive exons: chr19:9771396:9771550:-@chr19:9770055:9770143:-@chr19:9768685:9768811:-@chr19:9767223:9767329:-

Skipped exon: chr19:9785691:9785720:-@chr19:9770055:9770143:-@chr19:9767223:9767329:-

Skipped exon: chr19:9771396:9771550:-@chr19:9770055:9770143:-@chr19:9759363:9764557:-

Supplemental Figure S3. (continued)

Skipped exon: chr19:9785691:9785758:-@chr19:9771396:9771550:-@chr19:9768685:9768811:-

Skipped exon: chr19:9771396:9771550:-@chr19:9767223:9767329:-@chr19:9759363:9764557:-

Skipped exon: chr19:9768685:9768811:-@chr19:9767223:9767329:-@chr19:9759363:9764557:-

Skipped exon: chr19:9785691:9785776:-@chr19:9771396:9771497:-@chr19:9770055:9770143:-

Supplemental Figure S4. The complete list of TA ASEs called by rMATS that we excluded in our reported main findings. All sashimi plots are generated by rMATS.

chr10:29704286:29704341:+@chr10:29747203:29747449:+@chr10:29771762:29772361:+

chr10:38654362:38654544:+@chr10:38654362:38654557:+@chr10:38654546:38654557:+

38654362 38654400 38654439 38654478 38654517 38654556
Genomic coordinate (chr10), "+" strand

chr10:86185487:86185649:+@chr10:86259631:86259715:+@chr10:86273205:86278273:+

chr1:111889532:111889671:+@chr1:111890296:111890394:+@chr1:111891138:111891268:+

chr11:20101610:20101755:+@chr11:20104138:20104146:+@chr11:20104553:20104725:+

chr11:35211382:35211612:+@chr11:35219668:35219793:+@chr11:35232793:35232996:+

chr1:143915700:143916308:+@chr1:144053506:144053668:+@chr1:144094362:144094424:+

chr1:148346582:148346929:-@chr1:148344640:148344742:-@chr1:148343594:148343808:-

chr1:155033891:155033965:+@chr1:155034380:155034593:+@chr1:155034721:155034845:+

chr1:155180339:155180418:+@chr1:155180339:155182010:+@chr1:155182176:155182358:+

chr11:57529269:57529518:+@chr11:57529269:57529591:+@chr11:57556509:57556627:+

57529269 57534740 57540211 57545683 57551154 57556626
Genomic coordinate (chr11), "+" strand

chr11:830621:830713:+@chr11:830621:831295:+@chr11:831224:831295:+

chr1:183442856:183443033:+@chr1:183470266:183470402:+@chr1:183481972:183482003:+

chr1:183711261:183711424:+@chr1:183775509:183775619:+@chr1:183816700:183816908:+

85432003 85429678 85427353 85425027 85422702 85420376
Genomic coordinate (chr11), "-" strand

85439011 85435284 85431557 85427830 85424103 85420376
Genomic coordinate (chr11), "-" strand

85445786 85440704 85435622 85430540 85425458 85420376
Genomic coordinate (chr11), "-" strand

0

85437512 85434085 85430658 85427231 85423804 85420376
Genomic coordinate (chr11), "-" strand

85439011 85435284 85431557 85427830 85424103 85420376
Genomic coordinate (chr11), "-" strand

85429887 85429616 85429344 85429072 85428800 85428528
Genomic coordinate (chr11), "-" strand

chr1:207940358:207940540:+@chr1:207940358:207943707:+@chr1:207943666:207943707:+

chr1:208041271:208041368:-@chr1:207992307:207992491:-@chr1:207990582:207990759:-

208041369 208031212 208021055 208010898 208000741 207990584
Genomic coordinate (chr1), "-" strand

112450944 112435949 112420954 112405958 112390963 112375967
Genomic coordinate (chr12), "-" strand

112450944 112436970 112422995 112409021 112395046 112381071
Genomic coordinate (chr12), "-" strand

112450970 112441456 112431942 112422427 112412913 112403398
Genomic coordinate (chr12), "-" strand

112450936 112444058 112437179 112430300 112423421 112416542
Genomic coordinate (chr12), "-" strand

chr12:120703420:120703540:-@chr12:120662446:120662530:-@chr12:120661954:120662180:-

chr1:214503511:214503621:+@chr1:214504293:214507651:+@chr1:214507543:214507651:+

225161793 225183124 225204455 225225786 225247117 225268449
Genomic coordinate (chr1), "+" strand

chr1:225372993:225373127:+@chr1:225394670:225394922:+@chr1:225418775:225418853:+

225692756 225690842 225688928 225687013 225685099 225683184
Genomic coordinate (chr1), "-" strand

225695720 225693644 225691568 225689491 225687415 225685338
Genomic coordinate (chr1), "-" strand

0

225695720 225693787 225691853 225689919 225687985 225686051
Genomic coordinate (chr1, "-" strand)

225705009 225701747 225698484 225695222 225691959 225688696
Genomic coordinate (chr1), "-" strand

25571793 25571443 25571093 25570743 25570393 25570043
Genomic coordinate (chr1, "-" strand)

chr1:25570041:25570124:-@chr1:25570668:25571792:-@chr1:25571641:25571792:-

25571793 25571443 25571093 25570743 25570393 25570043
Genomic coordinate (chr1, "-" strand)

25571793 25571443 25571093 25570743 25570393 25570043
Genomic coordinate (chr1, "-" strand)

chr13:76378456:76378677:+@chr13:76381616:76382335:+@chr13:76383290:76383319:+

102025172 102024867 102024561 102024255 102023949 102023643
Genomic coordinate (chr14), "-" strand

chr14:103946724:103946827:+@chr14:103966493:103966537:+@chr14:103969219:103969618:+

chr15:25218866:25219603:+@chr15:25219789:25220104:+@chr15:25221452:25221563:+

53373627 53372966 53372305 53371643 53370982 53370320
Genomic coordinate (chr1), "-" strand

57953648 57964306 57974965 57985624 57996283 58006942
Genomic coordinate (chr15), "+" strand

chr15:63334957:63335142:+@chr15:63335905:63336030:+@chr15:63336226:63336351:+

chr15:63335905:63336030:+@chr15:63335905:63336351:+@chr15:63349184:63349317:+

chr15:63335905:63336030:+@chr15:63336226:63336351:+@chr15:63349184:63349317:+

chr16:30012250:30012361:+@chr16:30012533:30015978:+@chr16:30016542:30017095:+

chr1:6522923:6523030:-@chr1:6522923:6523207:-@chr1:6524435:6524513:-

chr16:686094:686239:-@chr16:684889:685063:-@chr16:684719:684797:-

chr16:686094:686260:-@chr16:685518:685774:-@chr16:684737:684797:-

chr16:686094:686260:-@chr16:685518:685774:-@chr16:685281:685340:-

69383555 69380686 69377816 69374946 69372076 69369206
Genomic coordinate (chr16), "-" strand

chr16:88925027:88925197:+@chr16:88925753:88925851:+@chr16:88926301:88926380:+

71478168 71446142 71414116 71382090 71350064 71318038
Genomic coordinate (chr1), "-" strand

chr17:7296110:7296271:-@chr17:7296463:7296828:-@chr17:7296786:7296828:-

chr17:74381532:74381735:+@chr17:74381532:74382218:+@chr17:74382066:74382218:+

chr17:76200909:76200981:+@chr17:76201684:76201834:+@chr17:76202027:76202131:+

chr18:32462033:32462165:+@chr18:32464692:32464740:+@chr18:32470264:32470507:+

chr18:33718233:33718389:+@chr18:33719382:33719576:+@chr18:33721100:33721164:+

56274672 56257972 56241271 56224571 56207870 56191169
Genomic coordinate (chr18), "-" strand

56274672 56259003 56243334 56227664 56211995 56196325
Genomic coordinate (chr18), "-" strand

chr18:690549:690631:-@chr18:690549:690745:-@chr18:693882:693908:-

2098435 2098508 2098581 2098655 2098728 2098802
Genomic coordinate (chr19), "+" strand

39224845 39224745 39224645 39224545 39224445 39224345
Genomic coordinate (chr19), "-" strand

chr1:94016504:94016662:+@chr1:94016504:94020216:+@chr1:94017966:94020216:+

94016504 94017246 94017988 94018730 94019472 94020215
Genomic coordinate (chr1, "+" strand)

chr19:50016644:50016730:+@chr19:50024952:50025070:+@chr19:50027764:50028033:+

chr1:95699759:95699871:+@chr1:95705333:95705465:+@chr1:95712312:95712773:+

chr20:30149437:30149539:+@chr20:30155881:30156027:+@chr20:30156923:30157370:+

chr20:30149437:30149539:+@chr20:30155881:30156083:+@chr20:30156923:30157370:+

chr2:135696572:135696632:+@chr2:135703357:135703552:+@chr2:135703671:135703784:+

169923545 169928528 169933511 169938495 169943478 169948462
Genomic coordinate (chr2), "+" strand

chr22:24121374:24121555:+@chr22:24121374:24122689:+@chr22:24122546:24122689:+

234299049 234308153 234317257 234326361 234335465 234344569
Genomic coordinate (chr2), "+" strand

234299049 234308256 234317463 234326671 234335878 234345086
Genomic coordinate (chr2), "+" strand

chr2:238305370:238305490:-@chr2:238303230:238303847:-@chr2:238296225:238296827:-

38313714 38315381 38317048 38318715 38320382 38322049
Genomic coordinate (chr22), "+" strand

chr22:46751341:46751485:+@chr22:46751341:46753234:+@chr22:46752739:46753234:+

46751341 46751719 46752097 46752476 46752854 46753233
Genomic coordinate (chr22), "+" strand

chr2:61021106:61021326:+@chr2:61021106:61022155:+@chr2:61022099:61022155:+

70286813 70274215 70261616 70249018 70236419 70223820
Genomic coordinate (chr2), "-" strand

70312757 70294970 70277183 70259395 70241608 70223820
Genomic coordinate (chr2), "-" strand

chr2:74686565:74686689:+@chr2:74686565:74686872:+@chr2:74686770:74686872:+

Genomic coordinate (chr2), "-" strand

111451344 111487584 111523825 111560066 111596307 111632548
Genomic coordinate (chr3), "+" strand

124896819 124882721 124868623 124854524 124840426 124826327
Genomic coordinate (chr3), "-" strand

chr3:129123093:129123246:-@chr3:129121366:129123246:-@chr3:129121366:129121422:-

129123247 129122872 129122496 129122120 129121744 129121368
Genomic coordinate (chr3), "-" strand

chr3:142342249:142342404:+@chr3:142364138:142364422:+@chr3:142383044:142383149:+

chr3:37163126:37163182:-@chr3:37162983:37163027:-@chr3:37138107:37138151:-@chr3:37136283:37136399:

37163183 37157804 37152424 37147045 37141665 37136285
Genomic coordinate (chr3), "-" strand

chr3:52356425:52356791:+@chr3:52357824:52357896:+@chr3:52360156:52360330:+

chr3:9944515:9944748:+@chr3:9945081:9945096:+@chr3:9948390:9948549:+

chr4:183837034:183837041:-@chr4:183837439:183837692:-@chr4:183837572:183837692:-

183837693 183837562 183837431 183837299 183837168 183837036

Genomic coordinate (chr4), "-" strand

0

83772758 83768238 83763717 83759197 83754676 83750155
Genomic coordinate (chr4), "-" strand

chr5:138614740:138614818:+@chr5:138615624:138615747:+@chr5:138618428:138618678:+

chr5:176919406:176919436:-@chr5:176918808:176918996:-@chr5:176918405:176918421:-

chr6:137147457:137147607:+@chr6:137191028:137191141:+@chr6:137219280:137219379:+

chr6:137167211:137167319:+@chr6:137191028:137191141:+@chr6:137219280:137219379:+

chr6:137167211:137167319:+@chr6:137193336:137193391:+@chr6:137219280:137219379:+

chr6:31940129:31940288:+@chr6:31940398:31940696:+@chr6:31946680:31946775:+

44187393 44189419 44191446 44193473 44195500 44197527
Genomic coordinate (chr6), "+" strand

chr6:44191351:44191378:+@chr6:44193710:44193904:+@chr6:44195000:44195079:+

chr6:76602247:76602407:+@chr6:76604531:76604557:+@chr6:76617322:76617425:+

chr6:76602247:76602407:+@chr6:76608090:76608128:+@chr6:76617322:76617425:+

chr6:87923432:87923583:+@chr6:87924716:87924860:+@chr6:87925621:87925775:+

chr7:102016659:102016769:+@chr7:102036424:102036984:+@chr7:102038067:102038145:+

chr7:102016659:102016769:+@chr7:102036424:102036984:+@chr7:102039995:102040095:+

102608565 102600197 102591829 102583460 102575092 102566723
Genomic coordinate (chr7), "-" strand

chr7:134617739:134618141:+@chr7:134617739:134618828:+@chr7:134620439:134620516:+

chr7:44796024:44796138:+@chr7:44796574:44796748:+@chr7:44796642:44796748:+

chr7:56140690:56140804:+@chr7:56141807:56141911:+@chr7:56142279:56142429:+

chr7:64275296:64275422:+@chr7:64291318:64291454:+@chr7:64291829:64292181:+

chr7:75039645:75039743:+@chr7:75042067:75042210:+@chr7:75044163:75044301:+

chr8:42202471:42202537:+@chr8:42211935:42212039:+@chr8:42213034:42213085:+

128024110 128029320 128034530 128039740 128044950 128050161
Genomic coordinate (chr9), "+" strand

140332537 140332225 140331913 140331600 140331288 140330975
Genomic coordinate (chr9, "-" strand)

chr9:2158456:2158587:+@chr9:2158456:2158978:+@chr9:2159814:2159909:+

2158456 2158746 2159036 2159327 2159617 2159908
Genomic coordinate (chr9), "+" strand

118763472 118761433 118759393 118757354 118755314 118753274
Genomic coordinate (chrX), "-" strand

chrX:131623842:131623996:-@chrX:131573463:131573600:-@chrX:131540256:131540420:-

chrX:153647882:153647962:+@chrX:153647882:153648085:+@chrX:153648371:153648433:+

153647882 153647992 153648102 153648212 153648322 153648432
Genomic coordinate (chrX), "+" strand

chrX:153647882:153647962:+@chrX:153647882:153648433:+@chrX:153648371:153648433:+

chrX:49021045:49021127:+@chrX:49021045:49021428:+@chrX:49021528:49021699:+

49021045 49021175 49021306 49021436 49021567 49021698
Genomic coordinate (chrX), "+" strand

chrX:49021045:49021127:+@chrX:49021201:49021428:+@chrX:49021528:49021699:+

chrX:49021045:49021127:+@chrX:49021246:49021428:+@chrX:49021528:49021699:+

chrX:86071037:86071102:+@chrX:86082769:86087605:+@chrX:86087109:86087605:+

